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Michael Burrell

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Reference for a preliminary ruling: Disciplinary thoughts, indications and future in the European Union law

dr. Michael Burrell, Ph.D in European Union Law, Attorney at Law, UK

Abstract: The present paper is based on the analysis of one of the appeals of the EU, that of the reference for a preliminary ruling. The subject of the reference for a preliminary ruling is rather particular in its analysis given that in practice it also occupies the national judge. The problems regarding the subjects, the object of the appeal and, the jurisprudential practice up to now and especially after the EPPO are some of the topics for reflection and analysis which our investigation deals with.

Keywords: reference for a preliminary ruling; EU law; appeals in EU law; interpretative validity; precautionary measures; urgent proceedings.

Introduction to the reference for a preliminary ruling

The preliminary reference was a judicial protection for the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) offering the individual (as a subject) a substantial guarantee within the EU.

According to Article 267 TFEU: “(...) the purpose (of this function) is to guarantee the uniform interpretation of the Treaty by the national courts (...)”. It constitutes proof of the fact that the States have recognized Community law with such an authority that it can be invoked by their citizens before the judges (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). In consideration of all these circumstances, the CJEU itself affirms in practice that the Community constitutes a legal order of a new kind in the field of international law, in favour of which the States have renounced their sovereign powers, even if in limited sectors. It is a system that recognizes as subjects, not only the Member States but also their citizens, attributing to individuals, who are therefore subjects of the system, “subjective rights”¹.

¹CJEU, C-26/62, Van Gend & Loos of 05 February 1963, ECLI:EU:C:1963:1, I-00003, p. 23.

In the same spirit Article 256, par. 3 TFEU provided that: “(...) in specific matters determined by the statute the Court has jurisdiction to hear questions referred for a preliminary ruling (...)”. This is a provision that was inserted by the Treaty of Nice (Article 225 TEU) accompanying a proposal for the related regulation for the transfer of related powers in matters that are subject to continuous evolution. In practice it is a change to the Statute of the Court which was proposed and inserted by the former Article 281 TFEU. The CJEU considers that the case requires a decision of principle which could jeopardize the unity or coherence of Union law. So, the decisions of the General Court are subject to review by the CJEU if “(...) there are serious risks that the unity or coherence of EU law will be jeopardized (...)”. According to Article 256, par. 3 TFEU and Article 62 of the Statute on jurisdiction, the Advocate General can request a review, as a precise, central function of a particular and unique jurisdictional system (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021; Pertek, 2021). CJEU is the interpreter of EU law as stated by Article 19 TEU. It

ensures compliance with the law in the interpretation and application of the Treaty, however Article 256 TFEU states that the division of competences through the CJEU and the General Court are entrusted to a judge of first instance and simultaneously also to a judge of appeal according to the decisions taken by the specialized courts such as the civil service tribunal. With Article 19 (2nd lett.) the reference to the rule includes the role of the national judge as judge of the Union and is envisaged as an obligation for the Member States seeking to establish:

“(...) the judicial remedies necessary to ensure effective judicial protection in the sectors governed by Union law (...) in a framework of sincere cooperation (Article 4, paragraph 3 TEU) between judges, between Union and national institutions, so that the law is correctly applied in a legal system defined as a “community of law” (...)” (Barnard, 2019).

It therefore puts the protection of individuals at the forefront as we have seen in Articles 263, 267, 277 TFEU by establishing a total system of legal remedies and proceedings and entrusting the CJEU with the control of legitimacy in relation to the acts of the

institutions (Liakopoulos, 2022)².

Loyal cooperation “as a principle” between CJEU and national judge

National judges are part of a system of guardianship of the individual through their cooperation with the judges of the CJEU. We are talking about a cooperation that is based on the principle of cooperation, i.e. the preliminary reference where the national judges guarantee the execution of EU law, as well as the performance of the functions as the final objective for the protection of the individual. According to what the judge stated, judicial protection belongs to individuals by virtue of the provisions of Community law having direct effect³ and in interpreting one's own national law in the light of the letter and the purpose of directives in order to achieve the result

²CJEU, C-294/83, *Les Verts v. European Parliament* of 23 April 1986, ECLI:EU:C:1986:166, I-01339, par. 23. C-896/19, *Republika of 20 April 2021*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:311, not yet published, parr. 35-38, 40-41.
³CJEU, 61/79, *Denkavit* of 27 March 1980, ECLI:EU:C:1980:100, I-01205, par. 25.

contemplated by Article 189 (later 288 TFEU), 3rd paragraph⁴.

The preliminary reference has a nature of loyal cooperation where the CJEU exercises a role of evolution of the EU thus contributing to a system of the EU that replaces and fills the gaps of the institutions within the legislative process of the Union. The CJEU affirms the general principles as an integral part of an evolving system of the EU providing a continuous contribution to the jurisprudential system of the EU.

Prejudice, national jurisdiction, subjects and right to referral

The reference for a preliminary ruling includes two avenues of implementation. A preliminary ruling of a temporal nature which is applied when the sentence of the CJEU precedes the sentence of the national judge and a functional preliminary ruling applied

⁴CJEU, C-14/83, Sabine Von Colson and Kamann v Land Nordrhein-Westfalen of 10 April 1984, ECLI:EU:C:1984:153, I-01891, par. 26. C-632/18, Fonds du Logement de la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale of 3 October 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:833, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 48. C-561/19, Consortium of Italian Management of 6 October 2021, ECLI:EU:C:2021:799, not yet published, par. 29.

when the CJEU functions as an instrumental body which respects the issuing of this type of sentence.

The jurisdiction of EU Member States presents a legitimate subjectivity which proposes an interpretation and validity of the rule of the EU which does not coincide with the relative definitions of the national legal systems. The judicial function has the objective of: “(...) ruling in the context of a proceeding intended to result in a judgment of a judicial nature (...)”⁵.

A judge of a Member State exercising an administrative function does not have the competence to propose a referral to the CJEU. In this case we are talking about a voluntary jurisdiction where the judge exercises the relative control function, such as for example:

“(...) the requirements of a company to approve the purposes for registration in the relative register of companies and the judicial not administrative functions at the time it decides on the proposed complaint that has been proposed by the approval (...)”⁶.

5CJEU, C-111/94, Job Centre I of 19 October 1995, ECLI:EU:C:1995:340, I-03361, par. 9.

6CJEU, C-55/96, Job Centre II of 11 December 1997, ECLI:EU:C:1997:603, I-07119, par. 2, 7-8.

According to CJEU, when defining the characteristics of a judge we must take into account a set of elements such as the legal origin of the body, its permanent nature, the mandatory type of its jurisdiction, the adversarial identity of the procedure and its independence⁷.

The relative arbitrator that has been established by the parties and the conventional arbitration board do not possess the relative characteristics given that there is no obligation, either in law or in fact, to entrust the resolution of one's disputes to an arbitrator. An administrative authority such as that of competition in Greece, but also in Italy, possesses these characteristics, lacking both the exercise of a judicial function and full autonomy with respect to the executive power (Sousa Ferro, 2021)⁸.

⁷CJEU, C-125/04, *Denuit and Cordenier* of 27 January 2005, ECLI:EU:C:2005:69, I-00923. C-54/96, *Dorsch Consult Ingenieurgesellschaft v Bundesbaugesellschaft Berlin* of 17 September 1997, ECLI:EU:C:1997:413, I-04961, par. 23.

⁸CJEU, C-53/03, *Syfait and others* of 31 May 2005, EU:C:2005:333, I-04609, parr. 29-36. C-198/01, *C.I.F.* of 09 September 2003, EU:C:2003:430, I-08055, parr. 62, 80.

The objective nature of the referral. Distinction between referral and interpretative validity. Competitive diversity between CJEU and national judge

The object for a referral is based on Article 267 TFEU and includes both the interpretation of the treaties and the validity and legitimation of EU acts.

One of the objectives of the national judge is to find the existential link between the interpretation and the validity of the ruling by the CJEU. It is interesting to find the distinction and underline the relative jurisprudence in this regard above all because the CJEU is presented to the national judge as the interpreter of the law of the Union and of the CJEU. Every act of the EU is subject to interpretation, especially the binding and not acts (Luszcz, 2020)⁹ and the international agreements (including the mixed ones)¹⁰. Through the reference for a preliminary ruling, the national judge finds in the interpretation

9CJEU, C-322/88, Grimaldi of 13 December 1989, ECLI:EU:C:1989:646, I-04487, par. 18.

10CJEU, C-300/98 and C-392/98, Christian Dior and others of 14 December 2000, I-11307, ECLI:EU:C:2000:688, par. 37.

“(…) difficulties in understanding or applying the sentence and can therefore make a second reference for a preliminary ruling, since the answers formulated are not or do not appear clear (...) even if the (first) sentence pronounced is fully valid and effective (...)” (Luszcz, 2020)¹¹.

The national judge thus enjoys the relative power to evaluate and propose a referral of an additional nature. As already stated by CJEU Article 267 TFEU gives national courts the broadest power to refer the matter to the court if they consider that, in the context of a dispute pending before them, questions have arisen involving an interpretation or a finding of the validity of provisions of EU law which are essential for the purposes of ruling on the merits of the case before them. National courts are free to exercise this power at any time they deem fit for a preliminary ruling as regards the interpretation or validity of the acts of the EU institutions in question. For the settlement of the main dispute, it must possibly depart from the assessments of the

¹¹CJEU, C-69/85, Wünsche Handelsgesellschaft GmbH of 5 March 1986, ECLI:EU:C:1986:104, 00947, par. 15. C-14/86, Pretore di Salò v. X of 19 June 1987, ECLI:EU:C:1987:275, 02545, par. 12. C-466/00, Kaba of 06 March 2003. ECLI:EU:C:2003:127, I-02219, par. 39. C-634/15, Sokoll-Seebacher and others of 30 June 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:510, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 19.

higher court if it considers that the latter do not comply with EU law (Barnard, Peers, 2017)¹².

In case of legitimacy judgment, the analogies with those of cancellation, according to Article 263 TFEU, are found at the moment that the acts that are subject to evaluation can be challenged for the relative annulment. They produce legal effects of a binding nature but not the opinions or recommendations which according to the judgments of the CJEU find their validity at the moment of revocation (according to Article 44 of the Statute of the CJEU). In this case the judge does not examine acts that enter into primary law.

¹²CJEU, C-173/09, Elchinov of 05 October 2020, ECLI:EU:C:2020:581, I-08889, parr. 26, 29-31. C-58/13 and C-59/13, Torresi of 17 July 2014, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2088, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 32. C-614/15, Sokoll-Seebacher and Nederhirm of 30 June 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:510, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 19. See the conclusions of the Advocate General in case: C-561/19, Consorzio Italian Management of 15 April 2021, ECLI:EU:C:2021:291, not yet published, parr. 29 and 30.

Reference for a preliminary ruling and national judge

One of the main objectives of the national judge is to decide by providing all the relevant elements of law which are useful for the case. A division of jurisdiction also means the corresponding responsibility of the national judge. The CJEU has no competence to rule on a case that concerns the national judge and the regularity of the national judgment since these are profiles that have to do with national law¹³. Furthermore, in the event of lack of indications, the CJEU is legitimate not to answer the related questions and to declare that the same are inadmissible. The CJEU has only the competence to verify the applications that are admissible as well as the factual and legal framework in which the questions arise and the factual hypotheses on which these questions are based in order to arrive at an interpretation that is useful for the national judge¹⁴.

13CJEU, C-435/97, *World Wildlife Fund* of 16 September 1999, ECLI:EU:C:1999:418, I-05613, par. 32. C-472/93, *Spano v. Fiat Geotech and Fiat Hitachi Excavators* of 07 December 1995, ECLI:EU:C:1995:421, I-04321, par. 16.

14CJEU, C-320/90, C-321/90, C-322/90, *Telemarsicabruzzo* of 26 January 1993, ECLI:EU:C:1993:26, I-02533, par. 6.

In this spirit, the useful effect is presented as a general principle of the EU where it realizes the relative cooperation between two judges (Liakopoulos, 2020). The useful effect recalls and affirms the duty/power of the judge to disapply the relative initiative as an internal procedural provision which, according to the useful effect, awaits the abrogation of the relative national law and the pronouncement of constitutional illegitimacy according to what is legitimated, is then consolidated by national jurisprudence (Coutts, 2019; Klimek, 2021)¹⁵. The national judge is the only one who has direct knowledge of the facts of the case in the most suitable situation to assess, in consideration of the specific aspects of the dispute, the need for a preliminary ruling in order to be able to issue the sentence¹⁶. When the interpretation of EU rules has no relation to the actuality or object of the case, the

15CJEU, C-614/14, *Ognyanov* of 05 July 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:514, par. 35. C-554/14, *Ognyanov* of 08 November 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:835, par. 67, both the above cases published in the electronic Reports of the cases.
16CJEU, C-83/91, *Meilicke v. ADV-ORGA* of 16 July 1992, ECLI:EU:C:1992:332, I-04871, par. 23.

claim is inadmissible (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019; Broberg, Fenger, 2021)¹⁷.

Within this context, the case of an improper and abusive use of the reference for a preliminary ruling is also mentioned. This it can be noticed when the national dispute is artificial and bogus¹⁸, when the Community law is inapplicable to the relevant case¹⁹, and when the questions are hypothetical in nature and not accurate²⁰. Thus the CJEU does not express itself at the time of a preliminary reference but according to the ad hoc request that is provided for by Article 218, par. 11 TFEU, i.e. when it deals with a question of compatibility of an international agreement with the treaties and requires from the CJEU, the European Parliament, the European Commission and/or a Member State their opinion.

17CJEU, C-291/96, Grado and Bashir of 09 October 1997, ECLI:EU:C:1997:479, par. 11.

18CJEU, 104/79, Foglia v. Novello of 11 March 1980, I-00745, ECLI:EU:C:1980:73. C-244/80 Foglia v. Novello of 11 December 1981, ECLI:EU:C:1980:302, I-03045, parr. 10-11, par. 18.

19CJEU, C-13/68, Salgoil of 19 December 1968, ECLI:EU:C:1968:54, I-00661, parr. 611-612.

20CJEU, C-83/91, Meilicke v. ADV-ORGA of 16 July 1992, op. cit.

With the expression opinion in the case of a preliminary ruling we mean an inappropriate term given that the CJEU can be pronounced in a sentence with an order with binding effect and with erga omnes value. The referring judge pronounces with res judicata effect on some points of law when it binds other judges, the subjects in general and, the States²¹.

Of course, there is also the moment that a preliminary ruling can be denied since that general principle requires collaboration between the CJEU and national judges in a limited way and in cases of a particular nature such as those which have to do with the interpretation of Community law or the examination of the validity of a Community rule which, under the indicated profiles, have no relation with the reality or with the object of the dispute in the main proceedings²².

21CJEU, C-62/14, Gauweiler and others of 16 June 2015, ECLI:EU:C:2015:400, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 16.

22CJEU, C-183/00, González Sanchez of 25 April 2002, ECLI:EU:C:2002:255, I-03901, par. 16.

Obligation to refer: Issues of interpretation, the obligation to state reasons, and “non-referral”

The qualification of the national judge is based on lett. 2 and 3 of Article 267 TFEU. When the judge with his decisions cannot propose a judicial remedy under domestic law (paragraph 3) there is an obligation to refer (a judicial remedy under domestic law must be understood as the ordinary remedy, not the extraordinary one). Otherwise (2nd paragraph) there is a simple option. An error by the first judge cannot be remedied and therefore there is an obligation for a judicial appeal under domestic law (ordinary remedy). In this case, the judge is endowed with particular authority, i.e. he has the obligation to prevent national jurisprudence from being consolidated in a Member State in conflict with Community rules (Borberg, Fenger, 2021)²³ and responds to the need not to cause damage to the judicial protection of individuals, otherwise deprived of a

²³CJEU, C-99/00, Lyckeskog of 04 June 2002, ECLI:EU:C:2002:329, I-04839, par. 11.

means of judicial protection²⁴.

The obligation is not absolutely mandatory given that the CJEU has introduced flexibility criteria where the judge of last instance must refer to the CJEU when the question of interpretation is distinguished from the validity of certain characteristics. Thus the faculty in the context of a judgment of last instance presents some important elements, such as for example the hypothesis that the question is materially identical to another question, raised in relation to a similar case, decided in a preliminary ruling, and the answer to the question it results from a constant jurisprudence of the Court which, regardless of the nature of the proceedings in which it was produced, resolves the disputed point of law, even in the absence of a strict identity between the matters in dispute. The rule of EU law is so clear or imposes itself with such an evidence that it leaves no room for any reasonable doubt as to the solution to be given to the question raised²⁵.

24CJEU, C-224/01, Köbler of 30 september 2003, ECLI:EU:C:2003:513, I-10239, par. 34.

25CJEU, 28-30/62, Da Costa en Schaake NV e a./Administratie der Belastingen of 27 March 1963, I-00061, ECLI:EU:C:1963:6, par. 73. C-

The hypothesis where the rule of EU law should be clear and evident leaving no doubts about the solution of the question raised derives from the theory of the *acte clair* and the principle in *claris non fit interpretatio* where the national judge proceeds with the relative prudence to verify the evidence. This procedure would also apply to the judges of the other Member States and to the court of justice, however taking into account the possible diversity of the linguistic versions of a provision and making a “comparison” between them. In the case of full agreement, the judge must take into account the unnecessary coincidence of “content” between the “legal concepts” of EU and national law. Finally, he must take into account the fact that each provision of Community law must be placed in its own context and interpreted in the light of all the provisions of that law, its aims, as well as its stage of evolution at the time of application of the provision in question (Luszcz, 2020)²⁶. The tasks assigned to the

283/81, CILFIT of 6 October 1982, ECLI:EU:C:1982:335, I-03415, par. 14, 16.

26CJEU, C-283/81, CILFIT of 6 October 1982, op. cit., par. 20.

national court impose an obligation with limited exceptions. The obligation remains subject to certain conditions where the role of the national judge is fundamental for the CJEU. The relative discretion/flexibility with regard to the ex officio preliminary reference is recognized to the national judge regardless of the request of the parties and of the content of the request which concerns the effectiveness of the reference and the procedural autonomy²⁷. The CJEU states that considerations of procedural economy and usefulness are for the judge, even if it may be advantageous, according to the circumstances, for the facts of the case to be ascertained and for the problems of pure law to be resolved at the time of referral to the Court²⁸.

The obligation or not of the postponement is confirmed with certain clarifications. First of all we take into consideration the linguistic versions which are drawn up between the rules of EU law where the judge is required to carry out an examination of

27CJEU, C-126/80, Salonia of 16 June 1981, ECLI:EU:C:1981:136, I-01563, par. 7.

28CJEU, joined cases 36/80 and 71/80, Irish Creamery Milk Suppliers Association of 10 March 1981, ECLI:EU:C:1981:62, I-00735, par. 6, 8.

the issues of the versions which are relevant and take into account the divergences of which he is aware, especially when such divergences are presented by the parties and hypotheses indicated for “non-referral” or exemption from referral are proven. According to Article 267 and in the light of Article 47, second paragraph, of the Charter, the motivation of his [the judge's] decision must bring out one of the three causes of exemption, referring thus to the jurisprudence of the Court and specifying the cause of exemption²⁹. In exceptional cases, the judge can turn to the CJEU when there are causes of exemption, as the main proceeding which allows the effects of an act incompatible with EU law to be maintained. This “exceptional faculty” requires detailed proof³⁰. The CJEU states as a general

29CJEU, C-495/22, Ministry of Justice (Concours de notaire) of 27 April, 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:405, not yet published, par. 31. Order in case: C-482/22, Green Ray Association of 27 April 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2022:404, not yet published, par. 41. C-416/17, Commission v. France of 4 October 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:811, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, parr. 105-114. ECtHR, Sanofi Pasteur v. France of 13 February 2020, parr. 68-80. Georgiou v. Greece of 14 March 2023, parr. 22-26.

30CJEU, C-144/22, Raimondo Bufarin Heirs Company Srl, of 15 December 2022, ECLI:EU:C:2022:1013, not yet published, parr. 50-51. C-379/15, Association France Nature Environnement of 28 July 2016,

requirement some limited exemptions which provide guidance of an interpretive nature having to do with waiver requirements. This evidence does not leave room for reasonable doubts and the conviction matures that the same evidence would also impose itself on the other judges of last instance of the Member States and on the Court, allowing the national judge to abstain from the referral and to resolve the question under his own responsibility. The Court not by imposing a detailed proof but by reiterating the obligation to refer, considers that the national judge is not required to demonstrate in a detailed manner that the other judges of last instance of the Member States and the Court would adopt the same interpretation³¹. We are talking about an obligation that is extremely difficult to be able to provide the relevant proof that

ECLI:EU:C:2016:603, not yet published. C-41/11, *Inter-Environnement Wallonie e Terre Wallonne* of 28 February 2012, ECLI:EU:C:2012:103, published in the electronic Reports of the cases. Order of the case: C-597/21, *Petroleum Center Rome* of 15 December 2002, ECLI:EU:C:2022:1010, not yet published, parr. 54-57. 31C-561/19, *Italian Management Consortium* of 6 October 2021, op. cit., parr. 39-41.

is indicated.

What are the validity issues of the referral?

When we talk about questions of validity to a reference for a preliminary ruling we assume that they are frequent and analogous. First of all they concern the obligation to refer. An obligation to refer that has to do with questions of validity. From the same treaty we do not have a precise note on the matter given that the obligation to refer provides for and has to do with the question of validity even if the judge is not of last resort but raises the related question *ex officio*³². This ensures legal certainty which is compromised if a national judge can declare an act legitimate. The CJEU can declare the invalidity or illegitimacy of an act. National judges can confirm the validity of an act by adopting precautionary measures, deeming the reasons

³²CJEU, C-251/11, Huet of 08 March 2012, ECLI:EU:C:2012:133, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 23. C-136/12, National Council of Geologists of 18 July 2013, ECLI:EU:C:2013:489, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 36. C-2/06, Kempter of 12 February 2008, ECLI:EU:C:2008:78, I-00411, parr. 40, 41.

for invalidity put forward by the parties to be unfounded, and rejecting them.

They do not question the existence of the community act, because the powers pursuant to Article 267 have essentially the purpose of guaranteeing the uniform application of Community law by national judges. However, it is particularly imperative when the validity of a Community act is in question with differences between the judges of the Member States on the validity of Community acts that could compromise the very unity of the Community legal order and undermine the fundamental requirement of legal certainty³³.

The validity of a reference for a preliminary ruling legitimizes the CJEU to check the acts of the Union, i.e. all the acts that are not binding. It is a form of an indirect nature that respects the cancellation action according to the former Article 263 TFEU which concerns binding deeds and can be proposed directly to

³³CJEU, 314/85, Foto-Frost v Hauptzollamt Lübeck-Ost of 22 October 1987, ECLI:EU:C:1987:452, I-00233, par. 14-16. C-119/05, Lucchini of 18 July 2007, ECLI:EU:C:2007:434, I-06199, par. 49, 53.

the individual who formally addresses the deed which is of general scope and invests it directly and individually³⁴. The invalidity of an act has as a consequence the effectiveness of a *res judicata*, substantial and precise differently from the annulment sentence where according to the ex Article 263 TFEU has as its addressee the referring judge who binds the judge who judges the same act, and the institution, i.e. the body which issues the act and which must take the provisions for the execution of the sentence as a hypothesis of deeds cancelled according to Article 263 in analogy of the deeds declared that are not valid (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021)³⁵.

(Follows): Precautionary protection

The protection of the subject is part of the reference for a preliminary ruling when the judge suspects the invalidity of an act, the urgency and the risk of serious and irreparable damage.

34CJEU, C-50/00 P, *Union de Pequeños Agricultores v. Council* of 25 July 2002, ECLI:EU:C:2002:462, I-06677, par. 45.

35CJEU, C-66/80, ICC of 13 May 1981, ECLI:EU:C:1981:102, I-01181, par. 13.

The national judge doubts the validity of the rule of EU law when the execution of the administrative measure based on this rule is suspended. The protection of individuals is based on a suspension measure which makes it possible to paralyze the effects of the contested regulation against them, otherwise it would be prejudiced or “compromised”³⁶, since precautionary protection must be guaranteed even in cases where it is questioned the compatibility of EU law with a national law and a preliminary question of interpretation of the system established by Article 267. The effectiveness of the provision would be reduced if the national court cannot grant interim relief until it has ruled on the solution provided by the Court³⁷. The CJEU recognized the legitimacy of the judge to suspend the application of a controversial national law, until the moment in which the

³⁶CJEU, joined cases C-143/88 and C-92/89, *Zuckerfabrik Süderdithmarschen and Zuckerfabrik Soest v Hauptzollamt Itzehoe and Hauptzollamt Paderborn* of 21 February 1991, ECLI:EU:C:1991:65, I-00415, par. 17.

³⁷CJEU, C-213/89 *Factortame* of 16 September 1990, ECLI:EU:C:1990:257, I-02433, par. 22.

preliminary ruling is pronounced, and the applicability of EU law is not compromised or prejudiced, and the effects are simply postponed, confirming, once again, the necessary cooperation between judges and the compliance, so to speak, of national law with EU law by virtue of the well-known principle of primacy³⁸. Within this context, the national judge seeks to control and verify the urgency of the risk of damage of a serious and irreparable nature when the act of EU law is not suspicious and the interest of the EU takes into account the financial risk which involves the suspension for the Union. The national court recognizes the right to impose the related guarantees as a type of bail or of attachment. The conditions are recalled and indicated by the CJEU where the issue of a provisional provision is requested. Precautionary protection has the objective of:

“(...) granting a positive provision that makes the provision in question temporarily inapplicable: the ratio of the suspension or of the precautionary provision is the same (...) it cannot vary depending on whether (the individual) requests the suspension of the execution of a national provision adopted on the basis of a Community regulation or the granting of interim measures

³⁸CJEU, C-213/89 Factortame of 16 September 1990, op. Cit.

which modify or regulate to their advantage legal situations or disputed legal relationships (...)³⁹.

The importance in the judicial system of the EU is to ensure a broad and better protection for the rights of the individual.

What are the effects of the sentences?

When we talk about the effectiveness of the sentences we are talking about the subjective sphere and the erga omnes effects as well as the in tempis effects for the protection of the rights of the individual and with regard to national decisions of a conflicting nature. Certainly the rulings of a preliminary nature are binding and in the event that there are still interpretative doubts, the national judge can impose a new question on the matter.

The CJEU has to take a position regarding the law of the EU and has no competence to interpret national law or to resolve the case at hand. It can only do so indirectly when a national rule refers to a rule of the law of the Union which can determine the relative

³⁹CJEU, C-465/93, Atlanta of 09 November 1995, ECLI:EU:C:1995:369, I-03761, par. 28.

content and reproduces the same content in question⁴⁰. The applicability of a subjective nature is observed and assumes a general and explicit value according to its effects even outside the concrete case and when ruling on cases of law in an effective and final manner⁴¹. The effective nature of erga omnes judges the question of validity of an act by an Institution and as the CJEU affirms:

“(...) as a direct addressee only the judge who turned to the Court, constitutes for any other judge a sufficient reason to consider this act invalid for the purposes of a decision that it must issue (...)”⁴².

Of course, the national judge may disregard the preliminary ruling in relation to the validity and to an act by analogy⁴³. It is superfluous that the case is resolved with an inadmissibility order by the CJEU. The invalidity has to do in this case with the

40CJEU, joined cases C-297/88 and C-197/89, *Dzodzi v. Belgian State* of 18 October 1990, ECLI:EU:C:1990:360, I-03763, par. 41.

41 C-69/85, *Wünsche Handelsgesellschaft GmbH* of 5 March 1986, op. cit., par. 13.

42CJEU, joined cases 114/76, 116/76 and 119-120/76, *Behla Mühle* of 05 July 1977, ECLI:EU:C:1977:116, I-01211.

43CJEU, 66/80, *ICC* of 13 May 1981, op. cit., C-461/03, *Gaston Schul Douane-expediteur*, ECLI:EU:C:2005:742, I-10513, par. 20.

obligation that the institutions have to modify and/or revoke the act declared as invalid⁴⁴.

The judgment of validity is assimilated to that of annulment. The connection between postponement of validity and appeal for annulment is indirect and allows judging the deeds that do not have to do directly and individually with those challenged according to Article 263, par. 4 TFEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). One limitation considers the need for legal certainty which is subject to the referral under examination of an act that the individual challenges during the two-month limitation period according to par. 4 of Article 263 TFEU. The referral can also be made *ex officio* which in this case is equivalent to an acknowledgment/right for the individual in relation to: “(...) the possibility of circumventing the definitive nature of the decision against him after the expiry of the appeal term (...)”⁴⁵.

The effect in *tempis* of a preliminary ruling has retroactive or ex

44CJEU, 66/80, ICC of 13 May 1981, *op. cit.*, par. 13-15.

45CJEU, C-188/92, TWD v. Bundesrepublik Deutschland of 09 March 1994, ECLI:EU:C:1994:90, I-00883, par. 13, 17-20.

tunc value. Thus the sentence indicates with binding effect that the rule must be understood and applied at the moment it came into force. The effect also extends to the relationships that arise prior to the sentence and to the relationships that are subject to judgment. The CJEU states that the object of interpretation it can and must be applied by the judge to legal relationships that arose or were established before the interpretative sentence if, for the rest, the conditions are satisfied and allowed for knowledge of the competent courts in a dispute relating to the application of this provision⁴⁶.

In case of cancellation of an act as provided for by Article 264 TFEU the CJEU limits the effectiveness of the sentence (ex nunc) over time, also taking into consideration various needs such as for example legal certainty, the protection of expectations and, the need concerning the legal relationships that constitute good faith based on a national legislation up to a certain moment which also considers as valid the uncertainty that determines the

⁴⁶CJEU, C-61/79, Denkavit of 27 March 1980, op. cit.

rules of law of the EU and its own interpretation⁴⁷.

The interpretative sentence *ex nunc* can prejudice individuals who with a judicial action or through an equivalent request would unduly compromise the judicial protection granted to them⁴⁸. The same criteria apply

“(…) considering the parallelism mentioned between interpretative and validity sentences in the event that the invalidity of an act is pronounced (*ex nunc*), since the individual who in the national legal system has brought legal action or proposed an equivalent claim (...) cannot be deprived of effective judicial protection, and therefore, his rights must be preserved (...)”⁴⁹.

The effectiveness of judgments is also manifested in relation to national decisions that are conflicting. The national administrative decision becomes definitive after a judicial appeal and when the internal remedies have been exhausted, and

47CJEU, C-228/92, *Roquette Frères v. Hauptzollamt Geldern* of 26 April 1994, ECLI:EU:C:1994:168, I-01445, par. 19. C-41/84, *Pinna v Caisse d'allocations familiales de la Savoie* of 15 January 1986, ECLI:EU:C:1986:1, I-0001, par. 29.

48CJEU, C-262/96, *Sürül* of 04 May 1999, ECLI:EU:C:1999:228, I-02685, parr. 107-108.

49CJEU, C-228/92, *Roquette Frères v. Hauptzollamt Geldern* of 26 April 1994, *op. cit.*, parr. 21-21, 28-29.

through a revocation generally permitted in the national legal system the decision is in conflict with the subsequent sentence promulgated by the CJEU, thus allowing the national judge to impose the preliminary question as a misinterpretation of the law of the Union⁵⁰. The national *res judicata* that is in conflict with the decision of the CJEU can “surrender” before the law of the Union when the principle of judicial protection is offered by the law of the Union when the actual enjoyment suffers the related prejudice⁵¹.

50CJEU, C-453/00, *Kühne and Heitz* of 13 January 2005, ECLI:EU:C:2004:17, I-00837, par. 26-28.

51CJEU, C-869/19, *Unicaja Banco* of 17 May 2022, ECLI:EU:C:2022:397, not yet published. C-600/19, *Ibercaja Banco*, ECLI:EU:C:2022:394, not yet published. C-725/19, *Impuls Leasing România*, ECLI:EU:C:2022:396, not yet published. Joined cases: C-693/19, *SPV Project 1503* and C-831/19, *Bank of Desio and Brianza and others*, ECLI:EU:C:2022:395, not yet published. C-119/05, *Lucchini* of 18 July 2007, *op. cit.*, par. 62-63. C-213/13, *Pizzarotti* of 10 June 2014, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2067, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 61. C-586/18P, *Buonotourist v. Commission* of 4 March 2020, ECLI:EU:C:2020:152, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 93-95. C-2/08, *Olimpiclub bankruptcy* of 03 September 2009, ECLI:EU:C:2009:506, I-07501, par. 24.

Expedited and urgent procedures

For a procedure of expeditiousness and its development it is necessary for the national judge to propose a request to the CJEU according to Article 23 bis statutes and Article 105 (Regulation of the procedure of the court and/or with emergency procedure) and according to Article 23 bis statute and Article 107 of the Rules of Procedure of the Court (Luszcz, 2020). The first element of acceleration concerns references for a preliminary ruling and the second only the references for a preliminary ruling which represent a special alternative to the ordinary procedure and which express reasons for the referring judge with separate questions which respect the urgent reference and the point of view of the judge according to the issues that are being considered.

The urgent procedure is applied according to Title V, third part of the TFEU which enters into the matter of the area of freedom, security and justice by ordering the request of the national judge as well as ex officio by the president of the CJEU according to

the procedure of urgency foreseen by Article 107, par. 3 where it seems to impose it at first sight. In the case of an expedited procedure, the President must first hear the rapporteur judge and the Advocate General and fix the relative date of the hearing. On the other hand, in the urgent procedure the decision is taken according to Article 108 of the rules of procedure of the court. Matters which need to be dealt with urgently are explicitly indicated in the Treaty and in the rules of procedure except in the case where according to Article 267, lett. 4 TFEU the question referred concerns a person who is in *vinculis*. According to the “recommendations to national judges” some hypotheses for the accelerated procedure are clarified, namely:

“(...) high and imminent risks to public health or the environment, which a rapid decision of the Court can help to prevent, or when particular circumstances make it necessary to remove in a very short time uncertainties concerning fundamental questions of national constitutional law and of Union law (...) if the answer given to the question raised is decisive for assessing the legal position of that person (...)”.

With regard to disputes relating to parental responsibility and the custody of children who are in infancy, the outcome of the

dispute, where the main proceedings depend on the answer to the question referred for a preliminary ruling, recourse to the ordinary procedure, can absolutely damage the relationship between the minor and his parents and his own development as well as the integration into his own family and his social environment.

In cases of extreme urgency, the written phase of a proceeding that takes place before the CJEU is omitted and the Advocate General does not offer conclusions on the matter but participates only orally and specifies that the reasons for urgency do not depend on evaluations of an economic nature and/or pending from other similar proceedings involving other persons⁵². The urgency and speed of a case must be balanced. If this were not the case, the fundamental principle of effectiveness distinguishes the process that takes place before the CJEU and compromises the rights at stake and the personal freedom of the individual or

⁵²CJEU, C-700/21, O.G. (Mandat d'arrêt européen à l'encontre d'un ressortissant d'un État tiers) of 06 June 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:444, not yet published, parr. 27-28.

the related rights of the minor as fundamental rights of the person, including everything that is provided for by the articles of the CFREU.

Conclusions

In recent years, the regulation establishing the European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO) provided for judicial review by national judges on procedural acts which are intended to produce the related effects of a legal nature against third parties and recognizes the CJEU a preliminary ruling jurisdiction which has to do with the validity of the procedural documents⁵³ according to Article 42, par. 2, lit. a), a question which is referred to a national court. According to par. 2 of Article 42, lett. b) the interpretation and dispositive validity of Union law is repetitive and as provided for by Article 267 TFEU (Blanke, Mangiemalli, 2021), as well as on the interpretation of the rules that have to do with

⁵³Council Regulation (EU) 2017/1939 of 12 October 2017 implementing enhanced cooperation on the establishment of the European Public Prosecutor's Office ("the EPPO"), OJ L 283, 31.10.2017, p. 1-71.

the regulation concerning conflicts of competence between the EPPO and the national authorities according to Article 42, par. 2, lit. c).

Moreover, the related agreement that established the unified patent court took into consideration the court of first instance and the court of appeal which decides in the appeal that is legitimate and raises questions of a preliminary nature that we'll see about the next years. The Tribunal is like a national judge who respects the law of the EU and who is not obliged to take into consideration the primacy recognized, pursuant to Article 20 and the jurisdiction of the court of appeal to the CJEU. Thus according to Article 21 of the agreement, the court common to the contracting Member States and part of their judicial system, cooperates with the Court of Justice (whose decisions "are binding", Article 21) and guarantees the correct application and uniform interpretation of the Union law, as for any national court to which it is equivalent⁵⁴.

⁵⁴CJEU, C-281/22, G.K. and others (Parquet européen), conclusions of the Advocate General in case *Ćapeta* of 22 June 2023, op. cit.

The cooperation between the national judge and the CJEU is still a way of referring for a preliminary ruling now confirmed in theory and which we will see through ad hoc cases in the coming years. The reference for a preliminary ruling as an important appeal since the birth of the EU has always had the attention of scholars as well as of the institutions themselves. We are sure that the reforms will continue also in the near future both in the context of the EU as well as in the domestic law of the Member States of the EU, bringing into play not only the protection of the subject but also the basic principles of the EU law.

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